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THE ROLE OF NON-STANDARD PROBLEMS IN DEVELOPING PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' LOGICAL THINKING (A CASE STUDY OF GRADE 4 STUDENTS)

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Annotation. This article discusses the methodological aspects of using non-standard problems in Grade 4 mathematics lessons to develop students' logical and independent thinking skills. The content of the textbook by Bikbayeva N. U. is analyzed, and the practical significance of such tasks is justified based on the experience of the International Kangaroo Mathematics Competition.

Keywords: non-standard tasks, logical thinking, independent thinking, primary school, mathematics methodology.

Creative ability is commonly defined as the capacity to create something new that was previously unknown—such as prospective images, knowledge, goals, ideas, driving factors of action, and cognitive motivation. Given the diversity of viewpoints and interpretations, we examine the concept of developing creative ability through non-standard problems based on research devoted to the issues of mathematics education. The topic “Using Non-Standard Problems in Primary School Mathematics Lessons” currently serves as a “bridge” for applying mathematical knowledge to practical problem-solving situations.

An analysis of mathematics textbooks shows that, under certain conditions, any word problem may be considered non-standard, while under different conditions it may be regarded as ordinary or standard. Based on an examination of the theory and practice of using non-standard problems in mathematics teaching, it is possible to identify both their general and specific educational roles.

Non-standard problems:

- Teach children not only to use ready-made algorithms but also to independently discover new methods of problem solving, thereby encouraging them to find original solution strategies;
- Contribute to the development of students' ingenuity and intellectual resourcefulness;
- Help prevent the formation of incorrect reasoning patterns in problem solving, eliminate misconceptions in students' knowledge and skills, discover new relationships within knowledge, apply acquired knowledge in new situations, and master algorithmic methods for developing various forms of mental activity;

- Create favorable conditions for increasing the depth and durability of students' knowledge and ensure the conscious and meaningful acquisition of mathematical concepts.

Non-standard problems are rarely encountered in the current Grade 4 mathematics textbook. After conducting a comprehensive analysis of the entire textbook, we found that the number of such problems is very limited. Therefore, we intend to develop as many non-standard problems as possible for Grade 4 students and familiarize them thoroughly with their solutions. As usual, the problems will be analyzed according to the chapters of the textbook, and we will also consider recreational mathematical problems as well as problems from the international Kangaroo Mathematics Competition.

The textbook mainly consists of the following chapters:

Chapter 1. Revision of Grade 3 Topics

Chapter 2. Numeration of Numbers from 1 to 1,000,000

Chapter 3. Equations, Inequalities, and Quantities

Chapter 4. Multiplication and Division within 1,000,000. Formulas and Scales

Chapter 5. Fractions

Chapter 6. Constructing a Coordinate Grid. Spatial Figures

Chapter 7. Representing Data Using Graphs, Charts, and Tables

It is necessary to provide non-standard problems regularly while remaining within the scope of the topics covered in these chapters.

Chapter 2 includes topics such as comparing numbers within one million, addition and subtraction, plane geometric figures, and cut-out and foldable polygons. Below, we present non-standard problems that incorporate one of these topics.

Problem 1. Three boxes contain flour, sugar, and rice. The first box is labeled "sugar," the second box is labeled "flour," and the third box is labeled "sugar or rice." It is known that none of the products matches the label on its box. Determine which product is contained in each of the three boxes.

Solution. According to the condition of the problem, the contents of the boxes do not correspond to the labels attached to them. Therefore, the third box cannot contain either sugar or rice; consequently, it must contain flour.

Since the first box cannot contain sugar, and flour has already been placed in the third box, the first box must contain rice. Finally, it follows that the second box contains sugar.

In solving this problem, we simply added the word "not" to each label according to the given condition, which immediately transformed the problem into a much simpler form and allowed us to determine the solution conveniently. We believe that students should also be taught to apply such original approaches when solving problems. The subsequent chapters will likewise be enriched with non-standard problems in a similar manner.

Chapter 3 includes topics such as equations, inequalities, arithmetic mean, mass-related problems, and geometric construction problems. However, no non-

standard problems related to these topics are presented in the textbook. Below, we demonstrate examples of non-standard problems that can be incorporated within the scope of the chapter topics.

Problem 2. A boy said to his friend: “I calculated that exactly 100 digits are needed to number all the pages of this small book, starting from the first page.” Knowing that all the pages of the book are numbered, can you determine, without seeing the book, whether the number of digits stated by the boy is correct?

Answer: To number the pages from 1 to 9, a total of 9 digits are required. Therefore, 91 digits remain for the subsequent pages. Since the following page numbers are two-digit numbers, the remaining number of digits must be divisible by 2. However, 91 is not divisible by 2. Hence, the boy was incorrect in claiming that 100 digits would be needed. If he had said that 101 digits were required, his answer would have been correct.

Since it may be somewhat difficult for students to visualize this problem, it is advisable to have them number the pages at least up to page 20. The students can then draw the remaining conclusion independently.

Chapter 4, entitled “Multiplication and Division within 1,000,000. Formulas. Scales,” includes multiplication and division within one million, formulas, scales, and motion-related problems. When selecting problems for this chapter, we choose examples that incorporate topics from both previous chapters and the current chapter. The developed non-standard problems may not correspond exactly to every individual topic of the chapter; however, they remain within the overall scope of the chapter content.

Problem 3. A wolf and a rabbit competed in a running race. One step of the rabbit is twice as short as one step of the wolf. If the rabbit takes three steps during the time the wolf takes two steps, which animal will win the race?

Answer: The wolf will reach the finish line first.

The student should carefully understand the conditions of the problem. The non-standard feature of this problem is that the speeds of the two animals are not explicitly given. Therefore, comparing their speeds is somewhat challenging. According to the condition, if one step of the rabbit is 1 meter long, then one step of the wolf is 2 meters long. When the rabbit takes three steps, it covers 3 meters, whereas the wolf takes two steps and covers 4 meters. Consequently, it follows that the wolf moves faster than the rabbit.

Problem 4. The distance from the village to the city is 32 km. A cyclist leaves the city toward the village at a speed of 12 km/h, while at the same time a pedestrian leaves the village toward the city at a speed of 4 km/h. After 2 hours, which of them will be closer to the city?

Answer: After 2 hours, they meet each other, and both of them are at the same distance from the city.

This problem encourages students to analyze relative motion rather than simply calculating distances. By recognizing that the cyclist and the pedestrian move

toward one another with a combined speed of 16 km/h, students can determine that they will cover the entire 32 km distance between them in exactly 2 hours. Therefore, they meet at that moment and are consequently located at the same distance from the city.

To approach the solution correctly, it is necessary to determine the distances traveled by each participant during the two-hour period. The cyclist covers 24 km in two hours, while the pedestrian covers 8 km. Thus, together they cover a total distance of 32 km. Since this is exactly equal to the distance between the city and the village, there is no distance remaining between them. Therefore, they must have met. At the moment of meeting, both of them are at the same location, which is 24 km from the city.

Problem 5. A football team participated in three matches during a tournament. Over the course of these matches, the team scored a total of 3 goals and conceded 1 goal. The team recorded one win, one draw, and one loss. What were the final scores of the three matches?

Answer: The team won one match 3:0, drew one match 0:0, and lost one match 0:1.

Although the problem may initially appear somewhat ambiguous and non-standard, a careful analysis quickly reveals the correct line of reasoning. The key point is to focus on the single goal conceded by the team. Suppose that one of the matches had ended in a 1:1 draw. In that case, the team would have already conceded its only goal, leaving no conceded goals for the remaining matches. Consequently, the team could not have suffered a defeat. Therefore, it is certain that the loss occurred with a score of 0:1. It then follows naturally that the draw ended 0:0 and the victory was achieved with a score of 3:0.

Problem 6. There are five houses located along a road. The distance between any two neighboring houses is 10 meters. Next to which house should a well be dug so that the sum of the distances from the well to all five houses is as small as possible?

Answer: The well should be dug next to the middle house.

The solution can be obtained through the following reasoning. Since the houses are situated along a road, they are arranged in a straight line. If the well is dug next to the fifth (last) house, the sum of the distances to the other houses will be

$$10 + 20 + 30 + 40 = 100 \text{ meters.}$$

This follows from the condition that the distance between neighboring houses is 10 meters.

Now suppose that the well is dug next to the second house. In that case, the sum of the distances becomes

$$10 + 10 + 20 + 30 = 70 \text{ meters.}$$

Finally, let the well be dug next to the third house, which is the middle house. Then the sum of the distances from the well to all the houses is

$$10 + 20 + 10 + 20 = 60 \text{ meters.}$$

This is the smallest possible total distance. Therefore, the optimal location for the well is next to the middle house.

This problem develops students' ability to reason logically, compare alternative solutions, and identify an optimal arrangement. Rather than relying on a standard computational algorithm, students are encouraged to analyze different possibilities and justify why the middle position minimizes the total distance.

Providing students with such problems is one of the means aimed at revealing the practical significance of mathematics and demonstrating its applicability to real-life situations.

The problem could also be solved in another way. Namely, each pie could be divided into four equal parts, resulting in a total of 24 pieces. In that case, each person would receive three pieces. However, the condition stating that the pies had already been divided into 16 pieces changes the nature of the solution and requires a different approach to solving the problem.

Problems from the International "Kangaroo" Mathematics Competition.

Problem 7. A girl named Mia throws darts at balloons labeled with the numbers 3, 9, 13, 14, and 18. Which numbered balloon must she hit in order to score exactly 30 points?

Answer: 3.

Let us consider all possible ways of obtaining 30 points.
We have:

$$3 + 13 + 14 = 30,$$

$$18 + 9 + 3 = 30.$$

There are no other possible combinations that produce a total of 30 points. Therefore, Mia must hit the balloon labeled 3 in order to score exactly 30 points.

This problem develops students' combinatorial reasoning and encourages them to systematically examine all possible combinations before drawing a conclusion.

Problem 8. As shown in the figure, Denis ties his dog with an 11-meter rope to a point located one meter away from the corner of a rectangular fence measuring 7 meters by 5 meters. Denis places five bones near the fence, as illustrated in the figure. How many bones can the dog reach and eat?

Answer: 4.

In this problem, one side of the rectangle is 7 meters and the other side is 5 meters. According to the figure, the dog can reach only 4 of the bones.

In non-standard problems, there is no single fixed method or algorithm. Therefore, students independently choose the appropriate approach depending on the nature of the problem. Experience shows that in a number of internationally recognized mathematics competitions, especially those designed for primary school students, non-standard problems are deliberately included. Such problems develop imagination, critical thinking, the ability to solve tasks in an efficient manner, and non-conventional modes of cognitive processing.

In recent years, the proportion of non-standard problems in textbooks used in general education schools in our country has significantly increased compared to

traditional problems. When designing such tasks, international experience is carefully studied, and the development of new-generation textbooks for the 2022–2023 academic year has been identified as one of the main priorities.

Introducing students to such problems enhances the practical significance of mathematics and contributes to the development of a generation capable of independent thinking and of performing tasks based on logical reasoning.

References

1. Bikbayeva N. U. Mathematics: Textbook for Grade 4 of General Secondary Schools / N. U. Bikbayeva. – Revised and enlarged 5th edition. – Tashkent: “O‘qituvchi” NMIU, 2020. – 208 p.
2. Ergashev J. Interactive Approach in Teaching Mathematics. – Tashkent: “Fan va texnologiyalar”, 2016.
3. Шердор А., Шукруллоев Б. Многофакторный эконометрический анализ в рыночной экономике // Science and Society. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 7. – С. 19-26.
4. Akhmedov Sh.B. **Derivative of a function and its applications in economics** // International journal of artificial intelligence. — 2025. — Vol. 5, No. 04. — P. 1605–1613.
5. Jamolova F. et al. ISSUES OF STRENGTHENING THE PRACTICAL DIRECTION OF THE HIGHER MATHEMATICS COURSE TAUGHT IN TECHNICAL HIGHER EDUCATION COUNTRIES // ILMIIY XABARNOMA. – 2024. – С. 37.
6. Sherdor A. TEACHING APPLIED MATHEMATICS WITH PRACTICAL ECONOMIC PROBLEMS TO ECONOMICS STUDENTS // Universum: психология и образование. – 2024. – №. 5 (119). – С. 62-64.
7. Sherdor A., Bektosh S. Optimization of the supply chain in uzbekistan: transportation and distribution of goods using the simplex method // MUNDARIJA–СОДЕРЖАНИЯ–CONTENT. – 2024.
8. Axmedov S. B. An innovative pedagogical approach to teaching the topic “Applications of Derivatives” // Academic Research in Educational Sciences. – 2021. – Vol. 2. – No. CSPI Conference 3. – pp. 37–41.
9. Ahmedov S. B., Hasanovna Q. A. The use of non-standard problems in the school mathematics curriculum // Modern Science and Innovation Theory. – 2025. – Vol. 2. – No. 2. – pp. 40–41.
10. Mohchehra T., Ahmedov S. B. Initial concepts in solving combinatorial problems in primary education // Journal of Pedagogical Research. – 2025. – Vol. 4. – No. 1. – pp. 58–60.
11. Ahmedov Sherdor Boxodirovich. Teaching methods of the topic “Matrices and operations on matrices” in economic fields // Central Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2025. – Vol. 2. – Issue 4–2. – pp. 19–23. Ахмедов Ш. Интеграционный метод преподавания определенных интегралов в экономике // Общество и инновации. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 3/S. – С. 320-324.
12. Sherdor A., Maryamoy T. APPLICATION OF SPECIAL AND IMPROPER INTEGRALS TO ECONOMICS: A COMPREHENSIVE OVERVIEW // ИКРО журнал. – 2025. – Т. 15. – №. 01. – С. 949-952.